

УДК 622.271

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COMPUTATIONAL MODELING OF A HEAVY-DUTY CAR TIRE ON ANSYS

Key words: Oversized tires (OTS), tires, chambers, rim tapes, valves, factors, wear, destruction, monitoring system, economic effect, heavy vehicle.

Annotation: In this study, the possibilities of reviewing and analyzing quarry-operated heavy-duty vehicles, the effect of tires on the tires of heavy-duty vehicles operating under the influence of key factors, the static variable normal load impact and analysis of the dynamics of the process of heavy-duty vehicle tires, based on programming and calculations in the ANSYS program, the development of a method of standardizing the tires of mining dump trucks has increased the durability of heavy-duty vehicle tires.

Tires are the only parts of a vehicle that come into contact with the ground, so they have a significant impact on the vehicle's performance, from safety to vibration/noise levels that determine ride quality. Finite element analysis of tires will require technologies for modeling complex internal structures. ANSYS offers special reinforcing elements for tire cord modeling. In the process of movement, the pressure in the tire constantly changes over time due to deformation in the process of interaction with the ground. These pressure variations resulting from changes in geometry can be modeled by specifying a hydrostatic fluid element for the internal volume of air in the tire.

Pic. 1. Movements (top) and pressure contours in the contact patch (bottom)

Pic. 2. Nonlinear static calculation

Pic. 3. Prestressed model analysis

Suspension improves ride quality and steering stability and, along with tires, is very important in controlling the vehicle's dynamic performance. It performs its function only under the applied weight of the car, so the characteristics of the initial state also play an important role. For these kinds of designs, ANSYS Workbench offers a calculation technique called linear perturbation. To perform a static/dynamic analysis of a spring suspension, it is first necessary to apply a distributed load from the vehicle weight to the suspension model and determine the displacement under the action of its own weight (static analysis). The example later in the article is a non-linear calculation involving contact between springs in addition to the tire modeling previously described. Then a calculation is carried out to determine the natural frequencies of the same model (modal analysis). All initial conditions required at this stage, such as displacements due to self-weight and initial stresses, are transferred to the modal analysis by connecting systems in the Workbench environment. Finally, the last step is the search for the frequency response of the structure (harmonic analysis). The input data required for analysis is automatically transferred from the modal analysis by dragging and dropping one analysis module onto another in the project diagram.

Pic. 4. Graph of heavy-duty automobile tire wear on pressure

Fig. 5. Graph of heavy-duty automobile tire wear on load

Fig. 6. Graph of the dependence of the service life of heavy-duty car tires on speed

Fig. 7. Graph of the temperature dependence of the resource of heavy-duty car

tires

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